

MONOGENIC DIABETES: THE IMPACT OF MAKING THE RIGHT DIAGNOSIS A COMPREHENSIVE OVERVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Monogenic forms of diabetes are often mistaken for type 1 or type 2 diabetes, leading to misdiagnosis and improper treatment. However, increased understanding and more readily available genetic testing have revealed that monogenic diabetes is more prevalent than previously thought. This review aims to provide updates on the current knowledge regarding monogenic diabetes. Specifically, it will examine the latest research on prevalence, improved identification methods, advancements in treatment approaches, and the role of genetic testing. By summarising the most up-to-date information on this distinct form of diabetes, this review aims to increase awareness and improve the diagnosis and management of monogenic diabetes.

Keywords: Diabetes Congenital, Diabetes That Develops in Infancy, Diabetes That Develops in Maturity, Diabetes of The Young (MODY), Monogenic Diabetes, Diabetes in Infancy, KCNJ11 Or ABCC8, Sulfonylurea

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INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus encompasses a clinically and genetically diverse group of disorders. While type 1 and type 2 diabetes are the most prevalent forms, many rarer subtypes exist. One subset is monogenic diabetes, caused by mutations in a single gene. Though only accounting for 1-5% of diabetes cases, accurately diagnosing monogenic diabetes has critical treatment and education implications for patients. Misdiagnosis as type 1 or type 2 can lead to ineffective therapy, faster disease progression, and missed opportunities to halt complications. However, with genetic testing and thorough diagnostic workups, clinicians can now correctly identify multiple monogenic diabetes subtypes (1).

Making the right diagnosis enables personalized medicine through targeted therapy, family screening, and genetic counselling. For example, some forms of monogenic diabetes respond well to sulfonylurea pills rather than insulin injections. Diagnosing the specific subtype empowers patients to take an active role in disease management. Beyond treatment, genetic diagnosis provides a clearer prognosis. Identifying MODY subtypes helps determine the likely age of onset and progression pace. Testing family members for the mutation enables early monitoring or preventative care. Identifying a genetic cause can also alleviate self-blame in diabetes patients (2).

However, realizing the benefits of correct monogenic diabetes diagnosis depends on improving awareness and testing access. Though genetic sequencing costs have fallen dramatically, insurance coverage of screening remains limited. Many physicians still view extensive testing as unnecessary. However identifying the specific aetiology provides the key to unlocking better, personalized treatment. Progress has been made with specialized assays and biomarker-based screening algorithms to streamline genetic analysis. Still, testing infrastructure and guidelines must advance to make sequencing routine in diabetes diagnosis (3).

Moving forward, research must continue elucidating novel monogenic diabetes genes and mechanisms. Contemporary studies on monogenic diabetes have largely focused on Caucasian populations. Expanding ethnic and racial sampling will give a fuller picture. Ultimately, accurately diagnosing diabetes subtypes provides critical patient benefits. However realizing precision medicine's full potential requires continuing progress in accessibility, guidelines, and research (4-6).

PREVALENCE

Monogenic forms of diabetes are estimated to account for 1-5% of all diabetes cases. However, the true prevalence is likely underestimated due to limitations in genetic screening and a lack of widespread clinical awareness (7). Recent studies utilizing broader genetic testing suggest monogenic diabetes may affect up to 10% of diabetes patients. The condition appears to be more prevalent among populations with high rates of consanguineous marriages. For example, studies indicate monogenic diabetes affects 8-10% of diabetes patients in Saudi Arabia (8). However, current prevalence estimates predominantly reflect cohorts of European descent.

Expanding genetic analyses to more diverse populations will provide vital data on the epidemiology of monogenic diabetes worldwide. Overall, the literature indicates monogenic diabetes is more common than previously recognized. Broader clinical screening and expanded genetic testing to populations beyond Europe will continue to illuminate the prevalence and ethnic patterns of this heterogeneous disease (4,5,6).

Type of Monogenic Diabetes

- Maturity onset diabetes in the young (MODY)
- Neonatal diabetes mellitus (NDM)
- Syndromic form of diabetes
- Congenital hyperinsulinism

Maturity Onset Diabetes in The Young (MODY)

MODY is a rare, inherited form of diabetes that typically develops before age 25. This defines MODY as a genetically inherited form of diabetes that starts early in life, usually in childhood or adolescence. It accounts for about 1-5% of all diabetes cases. This statistic conveys how rare MODY is compared to the more common types of diabetes like type 1 and type 2. The overview sets up the topic and gives a high-level summary of key facts about MODY - that it is a rare, inherited diabetes that starts at a young age. This orients the reader to the general idea of what will be covered in more detail throughout the review (9-12).

Neonatal Diabetes Mellitus (NDM), is a form of diabetes with onset six months after birth. Neonatal diabetes mellitus is caused by ABCC8 or KCNJ11 mutations (13-15).

Syndromic forms of Diabetes, syndromic forms of monogenic diabetes are less common, such as in Wolfram syndrome and these syndromes are caused by HNF1B and WFS1 mutation (16).

Congenital Hyperinsulinism (CHI) Congenital hyperinsulinism is brought about by genetic abnormalities in the ABCC8 gene, which results in an excess of insulin secreted by the pancreatic beta cells, which lowers plasma sugar levels (hypoglycemia). CHI is a rare disease, affecting 1 in 25,000 to 50,000 babies (17,18).

Table 1: Summary of Variation

GENE	PROTEIN	MUTATION	PHENOTYPE	FUNCTION	INHERITANCE
HNF1A	Hepatocyte nuclear factor 1alpha	Het	Macrosomia and hypoglycemia at birth, adolescent onset Diabetes	Beta cell transcription factor	Autosomal dominant
HNF4A	Hepatocyte nuclear factor 4alpha	Het	Macrosomia and hypoglycemia at birth, adolescent onset diabetes	Beta cell transcription factor	Autosomal dominant
GCK	Glycokinase	Het	Mild non-progressive hyperglycemia	Glucose sensor, first rate-limiting enzyme in glycolysis	Autosomal dominant
HNF1B	Hepatocyte nuclear factor1B	Het	PNDM (permanent neonatal Diabetes mellitus) with pancreas hypoplasia, RCAD (Renal cysts and Diabetes) synd	Beta cell transcription factor	Autosomal dominant
ABCC8	Sulphonylurea receptor subunit of Beta cell K-ATP channel	Het	PNDM, TNDM (Transient neonatal Diabetes mellitus) adult onset	Clousure of the ATP -sensitive	Autosomal dominant
INS	Insulin	Hom, Het	PNDM, TNDM adult onset	Production of insulin or insulin action	Autosomal dominant
KCNJ11	Potassium channel subunit of B- cell K-ATP channel	Het	PNDM, TNDM adult onset	The potassium channel leads to Beta-cell membrane depolarization	Autosomal dominant
WFSI	Wolframin	Chet	Diabetes mellitus and insipidus, optic atrophy, Deafness (wolframite syndrome)	Function of the endoplasmic reticulum	Recessive

SPECIFIC GENE AFFECTED

HNF1A-MODY has been extensively studied as the most prevalent MODY variant. Early studies using linkage analysis mapped a locus on chromosome 12q in MODY families, leading to the identification of mutations in the HNF1A gene as the underlying cause (19). Later studies revealed the significance of HNF1A mutations, finding they account for up to 70% of MODY cases in European populations (20).

Characterization studies have outlined the clinical presentation of HNF1A-MODY which includes progressive beta cell dysfunction and diabetes typically developing from adolescence through early adulthood. However, presentations can still be variable and show reduced penetrance (21). The molecular defects that drive the insulin secretory defects have also been investigated. HNF1A regulates the expression of insulin and other beta-cell genes. Loss of its activity causes impaired insulin secretion rather than reduced insulin synthesis (22).

The gold standard for diagnosis relies on sequencing the coding region and splice sites of HNF1A to detect mutations (23). This distinguishes HNF1A-MODY from young-onset type 1 and 2 diabetes. Clinical sensitivity is approximately 80% in techniques like Sanger sequencing (19). Targeted HNF1A testing enables MODY diagnosis even in the absence of family history.

GCK-MODY is caused by heterozygous inactivating mutations in the glucokinase (GCK) gene on chromosome 7p. This was first discovered in 1992 establishing it as one of the earliest defined subtypes of MODY (24). Population studies estimate GCK mutations account for around 30% of MODY cases, second only to HNF1A mutations (25).

Unlike other forms of MODY, GCK-MODY characteristically presents as stable, mild fasting hyperglycemia from birth onward, rarely progressing over time. Symptoms are typically mild despite sustained hyperglycemia. Many patients are often asymptomatic and only detected incidentally (26).

The GCK gene encodes a key glycolytic enzyme and glucose sensor in beta cells. Loss-of-function reduces insulin secretion at low glucose levels. Characterization of molecular defects has found over 600 catalogued GCK mutations that impact stability, kinetic activity and protein regulation (27).

Diagnosis relies on DNA sequencing to identify mutations in coding and promoter regions of GCK. Testing sensitivity is over 80% in patients meeting clinical criteria. Distinguishing GCK-MODY from type 2 diabetes has implications for prognosis and avoiding unnecessary treatment.

Diabetes insipidus (DI) is a rare disorder characterized by the body's inability to properly concentrate urine. This results in excessive urination and thirst (polyuria and polydipsia). There are two main types of DI: central DI caused by a lack of the hormone vasopressin, and nephrogenic DI caused by the kidneys not responding properly to vasopressin. This literature review will examine the current research on the epidemiology, pathophysiology, diagnosis, and treatment approaches for both central and nephrogenic DI (28). DI is considered a rare disease, with central DI estimated to affect 1 in 25,000 people and nephrogenic DI affecting 1 in 250,000 people. The incidence does not seem to differ significantly based on gender or ethnicity (29). Central DI often results from tumours, trauma, or other damage to the hypothalamus or pituitary gland that disrupts vasopressin production. Nephrogenic DI is often caused by genetic mutations, but can also result from chronic kidney disease, hypercalcemia, or certain medications.

Vasopressin, also known as antidiuretic hormone (ADH), plays a vital role in regulating hydration levels and urine concentration. It is produced in the hypothalamus and then transported to and stored in the posterior pituitary gland. When water levels in the body become too low, receptors trigger the release of vasopressin. This then signals the kidneys to reabsorb more water and produce more concentrated urine (30). In central DI, vasopressin secretion is impaired. In nephrogenic DI, vasopressin secretion is normal but the kidneys fail to respond appropriately to signals. In both cases, the bodies lose too much water through dilute urine.

Diagnosing DI requires a demonstration of high urine output and ruling out other potential causes like diabetes mellitus and primary polydipsia. Initial testing often includes serum osmolality, urine osmolality, serum sodium levels, and a water deprivation test, with supplemental tests to distinguish central vs. nephrogenic causes (31). Genetic testing can also help diagnose certain hereditary causes of nephrogenic DI (32). Distinguishing between the types of DI is important for determining the most appropriate treatment.

The primary treatment goal for both central and nephrogenic DI is to replace lost fluids and prevent dehydration. For central DI, synthetic vasopressin called desmopressin is the first-line pharmacological therapy to reduce urine output (33). With nephrogenic DI, managing fluid intake, restricting electrolytes, and diuretics medications are more commonly used (34). I

In severe hereditary cases of nephrogenic DI, transcranial delivery of desmopressin has recently emerged as an experimental option to bypass the kidneys' vasopressin resistance (35). Recent research has uncovered new genetic pathways that could provide future targets for drug therapies as well.

❖ Autosomal Dominant:

The majority of NDM AND MODY types are brought on by autosomal dominant mutations, which implies that if just one parent has the disease gene, the child can inherit the condition.

A parent who possesses the gene has a 50% probability of giving birth to a child who has monogenic diabetes if the mutation is dominant.

Fig.1: Autosomal Dominant

❖ Autosomal recessive:

A mutation, however, needs to be inherited from both parents in the case of autosomal recessive NIH (National Institutes of Health) external link disease. A youngster in this case has a 25% probability of developing monogenic diabetes.

Testing can reveal whether parents or siblings who do not have the disease are carriers for recessive genetic disorders that their offspring may inherit in the case of recessive variants of monogenic diabetes (36-40).

It is possible to inherit mutations from the mother alone (x- x-linked mutations), albeit these are less prevalent. Naturally occurring mutations are also less common.

Further details regarding the genes that result in autosomal recessive, X-linked, and other types of mutations that cause NDM (Neonatal diabetes mellitus) and MODY (Maturity- onset diabetes of the young) (41-54).

Fig.2: Autosomal recessive

Sulfonylurea ($\text{CH}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$):

Sulfonylurea is a medication used to treat KCNJ11-related diabetes, such as type 2 and monogenic diabetes. The genetic alterations in *ABCC8* and *KCNJ11* impact the SUR1 and Kir6.2 subunits of the potassium channel, which serve as a conduit between the pancreatic β cell's ability to sense glucose and release insulin. Oral hypoglycemic medications are called sulfonylureas (55,56).

❖ **Sulfonylurea drugs classified into 1st generation as well as 2nd generation;**

The primary purpose of the sulphonylurea class of oral antidiabetic medications is to treat type 2 diabetes mellitus. They have, however, also occasionally been utilized in the treatment of specific types of monogenic diabetes, which are uncommon hereditary types of the disease brought on by changes in a single gene (57).

Sulphonylureas are occasionally used in the treatment of particular subtypes of monogenic diabetes, including:

1. Diabetes Mellitus in Neonatals (NDM):

- Chlorpropamide, the first sulphonylurea generation (58-61).
- Glibenclamide (glyburide), a sulphonylurea of the second generation During the first six months of life, NDM, a rare kind of monogenic diabetes, manifests. Mutations in the ABCC8 or KCNJ11 genes, which control insulin secretion, are frequently the reason. Sulphonylurea therapy may occasionally be useful in controlling non-diabetic diabetes mellitus (NDD) by inducing insulin secretion from the pancreatic beta cells that are still functioning (62-65).

2. Young People's Maturity-Onset Diabetes (MODY):

- Tolbutamide, the first-generation sulphonylurea
- Sulphonylurea of the second generation: gliclazide and glipizide (66-68).

MODY refers to a class of monogenic types of diabetes that usually manifest before the age of 25, with an autosomal dominant inheritance pattern. Sulphonylurea therapy may be beneficial for some subtypes of MODY, especially those resulting from mutations in the HNF1A (MODY3) or HNF4A (MODY1) genes. Sulphonylureas can help improve glycemic control by increasing insulin production.

It is noteworthy that the administration of sulphonylureas in cases of monogenic diabetes ought to be directed by genetic testing and consultation with a medical expert who specializes in the treatment of these uncommon types of diabetes. For maximum manhood, properly diagnosed and treated treatment programs are essential (69-72).

Table 2: Chemical Formulas, Structure and Trade Names

DRUG	MOLECULAR FORMULA	STRUCTURE	TRADE NAMES
Tolazamide (Tolinase)	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄ S		Tolinase®
Tolbutamide	C ₁₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₃ S		Orinase®
Acetohexamide	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₄ S		Dymelor®
Chlorpropamide (Diabinese)	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ O ₃ S		Diabinese®

Tolazamide, also known as topaz a mide, is marketed under the brand name Tolinase and is available in generic form as tablets weighing 100, 250, and 500 mg. The suggested starting dose is 100 to 250 mg once daily, with subsequent doses up to a maximum of 1000 mg per day.

There is some evidence that tolazamide can be an effective treatment for certain types of MODY (maturity-onset diabetes of the young),

- Small observational studies and case reports have shown that some patients with HNF1A-MODY and HNF4A-MODY can be successfully transferred from insulin injections to oral tolazamide therapy.

- The mechanism is likely related to tolazamide stimulating insulin secretion, which can compensate for the underlying insulin secretory defect in HNF1A/4A-MODY.

Tolbutamide, also known as tongue ta mide, is available in generic form and was formerly marketed under the brand name Orinase. The suggested dose for tolbutamide is initially 1000–2000 mg per day in two separate doses, with the possibility of increasing to a maximum of 3000 mg per day in the future.

Tolbutamide is generally not used as a first-line treatment for monogenic diabetes, but there is some research examining its potential usefulness in certain forms of monogenic diabetes:

Monogenic diabetes refers to rare forms of diabetes caused by mutations in a single gene. Some key points about tolbutamide and monogenic diabetes:

- Tolbutamide has been studied primarily in cases of maturity-onset diabetes of the young (MODY) - a monogenic form of diabetes often misdiagnosed as type 1 or type 2 diabetes initially.

- In particular, tolbutamide is effective in patients with HNF1A-MODY. In small studies, most patients with HNF1A-MODY were very sensitive to tolbutamide and were able to transition off insulin therapy to tolbutamide successfully.

- The mechanism is because the HNF1A gene mutation impairs insulin secretion. As a sulfonylurea, tolbutamide stimulates more insulin release which can compensate for the genetic defect in patients with HNF1A-MODY.

- For other specific subtypes of MODY like GCK-MODY and HNF4A-MODY, there is less evidence that tolbutamide provides good glucose control. Other diabetes medications may be preferred.

- Outside of MODY diabetes, there is limited research on tolbutamide in other monogenic forms of diabetes (neonatal diabetes, mitochondrial diabetes, etc.)

Acetohexamide has been in use since the late 1950s and is classified as a "first-generation" sulfonylurea medicine.

- The typical daily dose range is 250-750 mg, usually split into two or three doses per day. For older patients, lower doses are advised.

- Common side effects can include hypoglycemia, nausea, abdominal discomfort, rash elevated liver enzymes or jaundice in some individuals.

- Compared with newer sulfonylureas, acetohexamide has more drug interactions and a higher rate of side effects overall. It may also have a prolonged effect on blood glucose lowering. Acetohexamide has limited evidence and uses specifically for monogenic diabetes subtypes. A few key points:

- Monogenic diabetes refers to rare forms of diabetes caused by mutations in a single gene rather than lifestyle or environmental factors. It includes neonatal diabetes and maturity-onset diabetes of the young (MODY).

Acetohexamide are a few case reports of acetohexamide allowing successful transition from insulin to oral agent in patients with HNF1A-MODY and HNF4A-MODY.

- However, sulfonylureas like tolbutamide and gliclazide tend to have better clinical evidence for treating HNF1A/4A-MODY specifically.

- For other monogenic diabetes subtypes like glucokinase (GCK-MODY) or mitochondrial diabetes, there is very little or no evidence for acetohexamide providing good glycemic control.

- Overall, acetohexamide has more limited data in monogenic diabetes and is likely not first-line. Due to its overall side effect profile, it may pose risks in monogenic patients.

- Chlorpropamide has been used in some cases of MODY (maturity-onset diabetes of the young), but there is limited evidence regarding its efficacy and safety:

- MODY refers to monogenic forms of diabetes caused by single gene mutations and often present before age 25.

- There are a few published case reports of chlorpropamide allowing a successful transition from insulin injections to oral medication in patients later determined to have HNF1A-MODY or HNF4A-MODY.

- However, most evidence is from small case series or anecdotal reports. Robust, large-scale studies are lacking.

- There is insufficient evidence that chlorpropamide would provide adequate glycemic control in other genetic subtypes like GCK-MODY or mitochondrial MODY.

- Compared to other sulfonylureas like tolbutamide or gliclazide, there is less support for using chlorpropamide as a tailored treatment for common MODY forms.

- Concerns with chlorpropamide in MODY patients include the risk of prolonged hypoglycemia, potential drug interactions, and side effects requiring close monitoring.

Table 3: Chemical formulas, Structures and Trade Names

❖ **2ND GENERATION**

DRUG	MOLECULAR FORMULA	STRUCTURE	TRADE NAMES
Glipizide (Glucotrol)	C ₂₁ -H ₂₇ -N ₅ -O ₅ -S	<p>The structure shows a central benzene ring with a piperidine ring attached via a carbonyl group at the top. A sulfonamide group (-SO₂NH-) is attached to the benzene ring at the bottom. A propyl chain connects the sulfonamide nitrogen to another carbonyl group, which is attached to a pyridine ring.</p>	Glucotrol®
Gliclazide (Diamicron)	C ₁₅ -H ₂₁ -N ₃ -O ₃ -S	<p>The structure features a bicyclic piperidine ring system. A carbonyl group is attached to the piperidine ring, which is further linked to a sulfonamide group (-SO₂NH-). The sulfonamide nitrogen is attached to a benzene ring.</p>	Diamicron®
Glimepiride (Amaryl)	C ₂₄ -H ₂₁ -N ₃ -O ₃ -S	<p>The structure is similar to Glipizide, with a central benzene ring. It has a piperidine ring attached via a carbonyl group at the top. A sulfonamide group (-SO₂NH-) is attached to the benzene ring at the bottom. A propyl chain connects the sulfonamide nitrogen to another carbonyl group, which is attached to a pyridine ring.</p>	Amaryl®
Glyburide (Micronase)	C ₂₃ -H ₂₈ -Cl-N ₃ -O ₅ -S	<p>The structure is similar to Glipizide, with a central benzene ring. It has a piperidine ring attached via a carbonyl group at the top. A sulfonamide group (-SO₂NH-) is attached to the benzene ring at the bottom. A propyl chain connects the sulfonamide nitrogen to another carbonyl group, which is attached to a pyridine ring. The pyridine ring has a methoxy group (-OCH₃) and a chlorine atom (-Cl) attached to it.</p>	Diabeta®, Micronase®

Gliclazide in many countries, but not in the US, gliclazide is sold in generic form and under the brand names Diamicon and Dianorm. For optimal glycemic control, the starting dose should be 40 to 80 mg twice daily, increased once a week. A daily intake of 320 mg is the maximum.

Glimepiride sometimes referred to as glimepiride, is prescribed at a starting dose of 1 to 2 mg once a day. From there, dosages can be increased to a maximum of 8 mg once daily, depending on tolerance and blood glucose levels. Glimepiride comes in tablet form in dosages of 1, 2, and 4 mg under the trade name Amaryl and in a variety of generic forms. Additionally, fixed-dose combos of glimepiride and thiazolidinediones (pioglitazone as Duetact and rosiglitazone as Avandaryl) have been made available for purchase.

Glipizide, also known as Glip'izide, is marketed under the trade name Glucotrol and comes in a variety of generic versions. Tablets containing 5, 10, and 2.5 mg of the medication are available as well as an extended-release version called Glucotrol XL. Starting at 5 to 10 mg daily is the recommended dosage. Doses may be raised to a maximum of 15 mg (standard formulation) or 20 mg (extended-release formulation) once daily, depending on blood glucose levels and tolerance. Higher quantities should be taken throughout the day in divided doses, with a daily maximum of 40 mg. Both generic and brand-name versions of the fixed combination of glipizide and metformin are available (Metaglip) (73-80).

Mechanism of action (K_{ATP} channel blockers)

By binding to and blocking ATP-sensitive K^+ (K_{ATP}) Channels on the pancreatic β cell's cell membrane, sulfonylurea depolarizes the cell by obstructing potassium's escape. Voltage-gated Ca^{2+} channels open as a result of this depolarization.

1. KATP Channel Blockers: KATP channels are found in a variety of tissues, including pancreatic beta cells and vascular smooth muscle cells. These medications bind to these channels and prevent them from being active.
2. Vascular Smooth Muscle Cells: - Potassium ions cannot be ejected from vascular smooth muscle cells by KATP channel blockers.

This causes voltage-gated calcium channels to open and membranes to depolarize.
 - Vascular smooth muscle cells contract as a result of an inflow of calcium ions.
 Vasoconstriction is the overall result, raising blood pressure (81- 86).

Fig.3: Diagram of the β -cell. Monogenic diabetes is caused by subcellular localization of abnormalities inside the β -cell. Beginning with the GLUT2 transporter's absorption of glucose, glucokinase's phosphorylation, or glycolysis. Insulin secretion will be hampered by dysfunction of the adenosine triphosphate-sensitive potassium (KATP) channel, which is associated with the KIR6.2 (brown) and SUR1 (red) subunits. Nucleopathies are caused by dysfunction of the transcription factors found in the nucleus, and diabetes can also result from lysosomal abnormalities and endoplasmic reticulum (ER) stress. GLUT2, glucose transporter 2; ATP, adenosine triphosphate; ADP, adenosine diphosphate. (87,88).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Many patients with monogenic diabetes continue to be misdiagnosed as having type 1 or type 2 diabetes, despite advancements in both clinical and genetic research. To enhance diagnosis, more insurance coverage is required for genetic testing. In addition, Caucasian groups provide the majority of the evidence on monogenic diabetes. Future research projects should incorporate a wider range of racial and ethnic backgrounds to guarantee thorough data for all groups. Overall, even though progress has been made, more work is still required to increase the availability of genetic testing, enhance the precision of diagnoses, and collect data from a variety of groups. With more research, we can fully comprehend monogenic diabetes and offer the best possible care that is individualized based on the genetic characteristics of each patient. New developments have made it possible to differentiate type 1 diabetes (T1D) from monogenic diabetes. The creation of a T1D genetic risk score and the use of a non-invasive C-peptide creatinine urine test have provided useful new tools for clinicians in distinguishing between these two illnesses.

When treating infants with particular mutations in the ABCC8 or KCNJ11 genes, substantial dosages of sulfonylureas administered early on are still safe and beneficial. Novel genetic causes of diabetes are becoming increasingly likely to be found as more extensive genetic testing techniques advance. Personalized care can be made possible by genetic testing, but to meet patients' health literacy needs, results must be communicated simply and effectively. All things considered, advances in genetics are making it possible to provide more individualized diagnoses and treatments, but patient education still needs to be a priority.

ETHICAL STATEMENT

Uphold the highest standards of personal behaviour, being truthful in all of our interactions and activities on the job. Be sincere in both our words and deeds.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors attest that they are free of any known financial or personal conflicts of interest that would taint the findings of this study.

INFORMED CONSENT

Using websites, review articles, and other sources to produce research content.

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